

Sensitivity of brown planthopper (BPH) to four carbamate insecticides at IIRI

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Previous field and laboratory studies on insecticide susceptibility of BPH at IIRI showed that field-collected BPH were less sensitive or resistant to some insecticides than the insecticide-free greenhouse populations.

For further comparison, BPH were collected in Oct 1982 from IIRI fields where insecticides had been continuously applied. The BPH were reared in the greenhouse for five generations without insecticides. The sensitivity of the 5th-generation BPH to four carbamates was

compared with that of the original greenhouse culture. Twenty 2- to 7-d-old brachypterous adult female BPH were used in each replication. A 0.1 µl of a serial dilution of each insecticide was topically applied with a Burkard micro-applicator. Control insects were treated with acetone alone.

The mortality was checked on TN1 24 h after caging. LD₅₀ values of both field-collected and greenhouse populations were 0.28 to 3.32 for all insecticides except for BPMC which was 10.38 for the field-collected population. The highest estimated resistance ratio (ERR) of 5.61 was obtained for field-collected BPH treated with BPMC, indicating that the field-collected BPH were significantly

Sensitivity level of greenhouse and field-collected BPH to 4 carbamate insecticides. IIRI, Jan 1983.

Insecticide	LD ₅₀ ^a (µg/g)		ERR ^b
	Field-collected BPH	Greenhouse BPH	
BPMC	10.38 a	1.85 b	5.61
Carbaryl	2.36 a	2.65 a	0.89
Carbofuran	0.85 a	0.28 a	3.04
MTMC	2.79 a	3.32 a	0.84

^a Av of 3 replications at 25-27°C with 60-80% relative humidity and 12-h daily illumination. In a row, LD₅₀ values followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level.

$${}^b\text{ERR} = \frac{\text{LD}_{50} \text{ value (field-collected)}}{\text{LD}_{50} \text{ value (greenhouse)}}$$

less sensitive (or resistant) to BPMC than the greenhouse population (see table). □

Pest Control and Management

OTHER PESTS

Effect of green manure and nitrogen on mole rat damage and leafhopper (LF) incidence in rice

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We studied the effect of combined green manure and N application to rice on incidence of mole rat *Bandicota bengalensis* (Gray) (Rodentia:Murinae) and LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenee) at the Department of Soils experimental farm, PAU, in 1983 wet season. The experiment was laid out in a factorial randomized block design with three replications. Plot size was 10- × 2.8-m. Soil was a loamy sand, Typic Ustochrept, with pH 8.2, EC 0.17 dS/m, 0.17% organic carbon, and

CEC 4.5 meq/100 g soil. Mungbean *Vigna radiata* (cultivar G-65) was sown the 3d wk of Apr.

In one set of plots, the mungbean crop was harvested and removed from the field. In the other, mungbean pods were picked and plants were incorporated as green manure 1 d before transplanting rice. The succeeding rice crop received 0, 60, or 120 kg N/ha with and without green manure incorporation. Thirty-five-day-old PR106 seedlings were transplanted the last wk of Jun. N was applied in 3 equal splits at transplanting and 3 and 6 wk after transplanting. A basal dose of 13-25 kg PK/ha also was applied.

On 9 Sep, the number of rat-damaged tillers was recorded. LF incidence was recorded on 4 Oct by counting the LF-

Effect of mung straw green manure and N on N content of rice straw.

damaged leaves on 10 hills from each plot. Plant samples were analyzed for N content by semimicro-Kjeldahl digestion and distillation.

When no N was applied, rat damage and LF incidence did not differ significantly for green manure and straw-removed treatments (see table). Rat damage increased with N rate in green manure treatments, and LF incidence increased with N rate in both green manure and straw-removed treatments. Higher pest incidence with N + green manure may be attributed to the higher plant N content (see figure). □

Effect of mung straw green manure and N on rat damage and LF incidence in rice. Ludhiana, India.^a

N (kg/ha)	Rat damage (tillers/m ²)			LF incidence (damaged leaves/10 hills)		
	Green manure	Straw removed	Difference	Green manure	Straw removed	Difference
0	0.7 b	0.1	0.6 ns	11.3 c	7.0 b	4.3 ns
60	2.3 b	0.8	1.5 *	22.7 b	9.3 b	13.4 *
120	11.9 a	1.0 ns	10.8 **	65.0 a	25.3 a	39.7 **

^a In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at 5% level. * = significant at 5% level, ** = significant at 1% level, ns = not significant.